

COVERAGE OF THE TOPIC OF BOOKS AND READING IN UZBEK, RUSSIAN, AND ENGLISH PROVERBS

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Abstract: The article examines the theme of the book in proverbs in Uzbek, Russian and English, and a comparative analysis of the importance of this theme for the development of each nation is made.

Keywords: the importance of reading, youth development, proverbs and sayings, the universality of the concept of the book, the uniqueness of the theme, general cultural interpretation.

In the era of technical progress, rapid changes in the socio-cultural sphere of life, a revision of the moral and ethical standards of mankind, special attention is paid to the younger generation. It bears great responsibility for the future of the state, its economic and historical place in the general picture of the world, the development of each individual country. Faced with a difficult choice of moral values and a modern, often politically conditioned situation, it is not easy for every teenager to find the right path and preserve the universal values instilled in childhood. A book can play an important role in this matter, because the book becomes our constant assistant, comforter and teacher. We all need a book, because reading develops us, we become literate, our circle of thinking expands, our knowledge connections are replenished. The time we spend on reading is considered the most useful work. In all world cultures, people have long paid special attention to reading fiction. Since childhood, we have all been acquainted with fairy-tale heroes and real heroes who, in the name of the Motherland, our people and the whole world, are ready to sacrifice their interests and even their lives to protect the weak and the poor. In other words, from the first days of our lives, we learn about the world around us from the books that adults read to us. Books help us understand ourselves, our thoughts, in different situations. Each nation, each culture has its own wise thoughts that help us to live, what to respect, how to act in different circumstances. However, despite the difference in mentality, cultural traditions, we have different views and common values that can unite peoples.

Proverbs and sayings, which are part of the treasury of folk wisdom - sayings with universal value and appeal, help to increase interest in reading books among young people and strengthen their role. The truths embodied in them, despite their regional, religious, national and other diversity, are, first of all, equally popular and in demand in all countries for many centuries. From general truths to specific recommendations, warnings and reflections based on human experience, the brevity of their teachings encourages each of us to act and behave in a certain way. When getting acquainted with proverbs, one can ask why people use them at all. As is known, proverbs usually do not serve as simple poetic decorations of speech and are not used to satisfy a person's need for a variety of philosophical expressions. As a rule, they are used for practical purposes in various situations of everyday communication.

Proverbs can serve many purposes. First, proverbs have always expressed and still perform a didactic function. With their help, we can teach people something, give them advice or help them in difficult situations, show them the most important things, suggest the right path in life. Secondly, proverbs are very often used in personal relationships. They can serve as a warning, suggestion, reprimand, explanation, excuse, conclusion or comment. Thirdly, proverbs are a means by which we can discredit someone or criticize someone. Using a polite form of communication, in a short, concise sentence, we can hide our thoughts and say what we would not dare to say directly in person.

It should be noted that in Uzbek, Russian and English you can find many corrective proverbs and sayings that show the respect of the people for the heritage of their ancestors and their knowledge - books, because these books store all the wisdom of the times. In the Turkic Uzbek language there are many proverbs about the incomparability of books, their role in the development of mankind.

The educated is a flower garden, the uneducated is a cemetery.

A book is a source of knowledge, a friend of the reader.

Knowledge brings happiness.

A book is a treasure, knowledge is wealth.

Russian proverbs also call for love and respect for books. It is worth noting that Russian proverbs speak not only about books themselves, but also about book readers.

To live with a book is to not be sad for a century.

To read books is not to play with your hands. (Reading a book is not a game)

A good book, but a bad reader. (The book is good, but the reader is bad)

A book will help in work, will help in trouble. (The book will help in work and in trouble)

Speaking of proverbs and sayings in English, it should be noted that they talk about the importance of choosing the right book and author, not just about their beauty or quantity, but about what is written in them.

Don't judge a book by its cover.

Choose an author as you choose a friend.

Like author, like book.

A book is a book although there is nothing in it.

A book is a book although there is nothing in it.

In addition, there are proverbs that have almost the same meaning, despite their appeal to different languages and cultures. For example, the Uzbek proverb "A mind without a book is a bird without wings," even in a literal translation, is equivalent to the Russian proverb "A mind without a book is a bird without wings." And the English saying "There is no friend so faithful as a good book" is close to several Uzbek sayings, such as "The book is a sure friend" and "The book is a better friend in the world."

So, good deeds and virtue do not choose countries, cultures and languages. Being a well-read and literate person does not mean having a certain origin, language or religion. The most important thing is a person's knowledge and worldview. The most effective source of influence on the human mind is a book. Books teach us logic, thinking; contribute to our development in various directions; develop the ability of a person to see the goal in front of him and find the necessary means to achieve it. The world of books is endless. Everything is

so attractive and interesting that it remains to wish everyone a long life in order to study and learn even a small part of this world.

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